
A BIOPHYSICS-INFORMED MULTISCALE MATHEMATICAL FRAMEWORK FOR CNS PHARMACEUTICAL PERMEABILITY

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ABSTRACT

The Blood Brain Barrier (BBB) is a network of tight-junction brain endothelial cells that restricts pharmaceutical diffusion into the brain and leads to inaccurate dosage. This research focuses on using a novel predictive model to simulate transport for 25 commonly used drugs in brain dysfunctions. Paper emphasizes the integration of Ficks and Einstein-Stokes Laws to derive a parametrized function representing drug diffusivity. The function is constructed on calculated values of j-flux, diffusion coefficient, radius, and polarity; viscosity is a constant to model BBB fluidity. The equation is integrated from t in $[0, \lambda]$, the barrier at $t = \lambda$, and yields a measure of moles limited when diffused. We devise a rank formula, denoted $H(x)$, to weight drugs with respect to numerical diffusibility. Inputs employ min-max normalization to ensure the domain occupies $[0,1]$, standardizing values. Weight scores produced are shown through heatmaps to measure total diffusivity. Results showed Levodopa and Temozolomide scored highest, with weighted scores of 5.22 and 5.13 respectively. Conversely, Vancomycin and Paclitaxel attained the lowest. These results are consistent through viscosity modulation, achieving similar rank distributions. This validates the model's accuracy. The model weighs chemical factors to produce predictive permeability scores, avoiding in vitro costs and time. Future adaptations follow inclusion of Markov Chains to model BBB movement.

Keywords Blood Brain Barrier · Pharmacology · Neurotherapeutics · Mathematical Modeling

1 Introduction

The Blood Brain Barrier (BBB) is a selective neuronal-situated membrane connected to the central nervous system (CNS) that acts as a permeable barrier for blood-contained elements, including ions, red-blood cells, white-blood cells, platelets, and larger proteins [1]. The BBB's purpose has a crucial role in creating a homeostatic and optimal environment for the CNS [2]. A recent study concluded the endothelial capillaries, a unique property of the BBB, excluded approximately 100 percent large molecule neurotherapeutics and approximately 98 percent small molecule drugs [3]. Besides structural rejection of blood-contained elements, transmembrane proteins ATP-binding cassettes (ABC) are able to further retract oncological drugs. For example, P-gp Efflux Transporters, a type of ABC protein, uses ATP efflux to pump out lipophilic drugs from re-entry into the BBB [4]. The combination of protein hyperlipophilic properties, tight-junction brain endothelial cell connections and pore radii of 200 angstroms [5], the BBB makes the permeability of both artificial nanotherapeutics and biological chemicals a challenging endeavor to achieve.

Due to the numerous variables involved in drug permeability, large-scale testing is necessary to assess drug viability. This poses many challenges however, as CNS-targeted drugs, which include drugs categorized by the BBB, are likely to have a higher failure rate, are experimentally slower than other drug experiments and are shown to have slower approval timings by review boards [6]. To combat this wet-lab approach, Black Box Models of Artificial Intelligence (AI) decrease the amount of time to note patterns in training data and circumvent approval from regulatory boards

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for human and animal hazards because of in-silico methods. While deep neural-net approaches create a systematic input-output methodology, results may be inaccurate due to the lack of mechanistic interpretation, in this case biophysical interpretation the AI has, which may misconstrue results [7]. Similarly, using neural net capabilities without inclusion of biophysical based parameters creates the hazard of inaccuracies, especially when it relates to pharmacokinetics. The Black Box perspective of AI could plausibly extrapolate biological results without considering human constraints on human systems, such as the BBB. This prevents the usage of standard AI models to produce accurate permeability models for multivariable systems such as the BBB without additional mathematical reinforcement.

This paper focuses on a deterministic physics-informed mathematical framework for calculating permeability of drugs through in-silico models. Not only does this approach use biophysical context, the framework consists of five variable parameters and is built off of Fick's Law and the Einstein-Stokes equations [8]. The framework employs a series of tests to measure the diffusivity of the drug of interest (DoI) under certain conditions, such as j -flux, viscosity, molecular radii, polarity, and its diffusion coefficient. A devised rank system is denoted as $H(x)$ uses a common standardization procedure, minimum-maximum normalization, to create a comparative scale of values [9]. $H(x)$ displays heatmap weightages of each parameter and their overall contribution to the rejection or acceptance of the molecule under standard conditions and compromised conditions. Compromised conditions are defined as biological, physical, or chemical alterations to BBB or surrounding neuronal space. Changes in these factors can deviate permeability by a large extent, and can be further seen through varying parameters, which this paper also investigates. The model is further validated through applying it to 25 commonly used oncological drugs and calculating their rank scores in comparison to empirical metrics. This process creates efficient and valid results for assessing CNS-drug viability under BBB tumor environment conditions.

2 Physicochemical Permeability Framework: Foundation Logic

2.1 Foundational Logic and Parameters

We define the foundation logic of this framework through set environmental parameters kept in place for this deterministic model. For one, we are assuming the extracellular environment of the BBB is an aqueous or semi-aqueous localized fluid from which solutes of varying radii are able to diffuse through in a Brownian motion. This allows Fick's First Law and the Einstein-Stokes Equation to account for the permeability assuming the space is aqueous. Further, the model follows that all solutes must use passive forms of diffusion throughout the barrier. Consequently, a current limitation of this framework is the exclusion of adenosine triphosphate (ATP), adenosine diphosphate (ADP), adenosine monophosphate (AMP), Na^+ sodium efflux pumps, or other energy driven transporters. This is due to the necessity for intrinsic modeling of sole characteristics of solute properties itself compared to efficiency of BBB-supported transmembrane elements. Additionally, all solutes used within the framework are centered around their spherical radii given through the molar refractivity value of the particular solute. The following paragraphs will expand upon the logic behind the Einstein-Stokes equation, the rederivation of molar refractivity volume, and explain a large exclusion of the framework.

The Einstein-Stokes equation, also commonly referred to as the Einstein-Sutherland equation, is the quantity representing diffusive power of a certain solute particle as it pertains to certain chemical characteristics. More specifically, it uses the variables of temperature, viscosity, and spherical radius to determine the stochastic force behind the movement of particles. This proves the necessity of an aqueous condition to be mathematically present, for these variables indicate how changes upon the liquid medium affect the speed and diffusivity of these solutes. In the equation, hydrodynamic drag is shown through the viscosity and temperature, both variables which are able to change the extracellular fluid of the BBB from which medicinal solutes are able to travel through. A more compromised BBB, as we will discuss later, will contain different viscosity values and characteristics which could drastically change the values of overall diffusivity. This isolates how inflammation or hypoxic tumor microenvironments could create entirely new environments from a difference in the medium.

A crucial component of the Einstein-Stokes equation is the variable r , which denotes the spherical radius of a particular solute. Due to the lack of known experimentation upon oncological drug treatments, empirical open-source data for spherical drug radii were limited. Hence, we use another commonly used value, molar refractivity (MR), to represent the approximate spherical radii of these solutes. This is due to the Lorentz-Lorenz relation, which can visualize MR as the refractivity of space taken up by all singular atoms and electron clouds associated within the overall compound. Condensing this into a solid spherical shape, we are able to estimate the MR to be an approximate volume. We can, therefore, use the following formula to estimate the spherical radii:

$$MR = \frac{4}{3}\pi(sr)^3 \implies sr = \sqrt[3]{\frac{3MR}{(6.022 \times 10^{23})(4\pi)}} \quad (1)$$

A large limitation to this framework is excluding the influence of proteins, glycoproteins, transporters, and other larger biological molecules which could contribute heavily to the discussion of permeability of the BBB. The main aim of the framework is to isolate the interactions between the solute and the BBB itself, since more compromised versions of the BBB could limit the influence of these proteins from what they originally were. For example, hypoxic conditions within tumor microenvironments could release harmful enzymes which could degrade proteins and increase overall BBB viscosity, hence slowing down the diffusion of particles compared to standard conditions.

Table 1: Physical Constants and Parameters for BBB Framework

Parameter Name	Value	Units
Blood-Brain Barrier Thickness (x)	200	nm
Standard Extracellular Temperature (T)	310	K
Blood-Brain Barrier Viscosity (η)	0.004	Pa·s
Concentration Traveled (dC)	1	mol/m ³
Boltzmann Constant (k_B)	1.3806×10^{-23}	m ² · kg · s ⁻² · K ⁻¹

2.2 Mathematical Derivation of Fickian Hybridized Equation

Following the introduction of two major equations to diffusion, we see Fick's First Law of Diffusion and the Einstein-Stokes equations as shown:

$$J = -D \frac{dC}{dx} \quad (2) \qquad D = \frac{K_B T}{6\pi\eta r} \quad (3)$$

Fick's First Law of Diffusion

Einstein-Stokes Equation

Next, we substitute them in place of D, creating a newer equation. In this equation we will remodel $\frac{dC}{dx}$ into a more condensed version of ΔCx to represent the change in concentration over a certain barrier of thickness dx :

$$J = -D \frac{dC}{dx} \Rightarrow J = - \left(\frac{K_B T}{6\pi\eta r} \right) \left(\frac{dC}{dx} \right) \Rightarrow J = - \left(\frac{K_B T}{6\pi\eta r} \right) (\Delta Cx) \quad (4)$$

$$J = \frac{-(\Delta Cx K_B T)}{6\pi\eta r} \quad (5)$$

We can further expand and rewrite all the variables as a function of J, as ΔCx , η , T, and r are all still variable and depend on the medium from which they are describing.

$$J(\eta, T, r, \Delta Cx) = \frac{-(\Delta Cx K_B T)}{6\pi\eta r} \quad (6)$$

This new combination of two pre-existing formulas creates a new hybridized environment with following parameters mentioned in the previous subsection. The negative sign implies that there is a decrease in the concentration of the particular solute from one side of the barrier compared to the other, essentially diffusing down a lower gradient. Fick's First Law also follows that diffusion follows a linear steady state manner, where the BBB is a uniform barrier and solute diffusion is the same across all parts of the barrier, reaffirming a deterministic model. We can also confirm this formula is viable through dimensional analysis, which result in $\frac{mol}{m^2}$, the units of J-flux. This hybridized equation is able to retain the value of hydrodynamic drag into the concentration gradient seen within the environment. This is the first of four core mathematical modules that govern the framework. This equation retains the physics-informed context into the framework.

In addition, we introduce a new relation which can model any viscosity specific changes in the BBB as shown below:

$$\eta_{BTB} = (\eta_{BBB})(\beta_{constant}) \quad (7)$$

$$\beta_{constant} \in \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (8)$$

Where η_{BBB} and η_{BTB} depict the values of viscosity in a standard BBB and a Blood-Tumor Barrier (BTB), respectively. The represents a scaling constant by which the viscosity has changed from the BBB to the BTB. This relation is necessary due to BBB conditions, such as malignant tumors, which could change the consistency of extracellular fluid and therefore the solute elements involved. When the BBB is impaired, viscosity increases as more RBCs, WBCs, platelets, and damaged proteins. Hence, we use the beta-constant to show a higher viscosity during a BTB. The relation can also be presented in an alternate form, shown below:

$$\frac{\eta_{BTB}}{\eta_{BBB}} \propto \beta_{constant} \quad (9)$$

Using the combined Fickian equation along with the viscosity relation, we are able to perform the first of three foundational tests which can represent the larger mathematical framework. This test is done to produce the J-flux in correspondence to the viscosity of the BBB along with physicochemical properties of the specific drug.

2.3 Temporal-Concentration Permeability Quadratic

After finding the J-flux values for each of the DoI, we perform our next test for the purpose of examining the permeability of the drug with respect to an in-silico barrier. This is done through constructing a temporal cumulative permeability quadratic which simulates the predicted amount of molecules which passes the barrier, which we will denote λ . The structure for the standard quadratic follows:

$$f(t) = -|\alpha|t^2 + \rho t + \epsilon, [t \geq 0], [\lambda > 0] \quad (10)$$

This standard format shows the function $f(t)$ as the change in concentration with respect to the change in time. The quadratic has a negative directionality; the quadratic represents the amount of molecules which pass a barrier with respect to time. The degrading amount of molecules from one side to the other side of the barrier directly represents the temporal-concentration focus. We add a variable of integration, τ , to create an integrable quadratic. To find the physical area contained within $f(t)$, $x = 0$, and $y = 0$, we produce the integral below:

$$f(t) = \int_0^t (-\alpha\tau^2 + \rho\tau)d\tau + \epsilon \Rightarrow [-\alpha(\frac{\tau^3}{3}) + \rho(\frac{\tau^2}{2})]_0^t + \epsilon \quad (11)$$

$$F(t) = -\alpha(\frac{t^3}{3}) + \rho(\frac{t^2}{2}) + \epsilon \quad (12)$$

Computing this integral, this quadratic is restricted within the positive xy plane and is to compute the amount of molecules which have passed the BBB or BTB after a certain amount of time, t . To finish this equation, we define the variable α as the $J_{magnitude}$:

$$J_{mag} = |J_{flux}| = \alpha \quad (13)$$

Where J_{mag} is the absolute value of the J_{flux} we found in the previous Fickian-derived equation. We also define ρ as the $\frac{D}{\Delta x}$, which is isolating the force at which the chemical is able to move over the area of Δx . Finally, we assign the epsilon constant, ϵ , as a brownian correction factor. This is due to the potential margin of error which could be created as a result of assumptions on specific values of a chemical. In reality, the behavior of the molecule could be due to other factors within the BBB which are extraneous to the sole behavior of the molecule itself. To account for this potential influential factor, we add a brownian correction factor. To make notation convenient, we represent the function as $f_a(t)$. Replacing each of the variables, we get the equation:

$$f_a(t) = \int_0^t [(-J_{mag}\tau)^2 + (\frac{D}{\Delta x}\tau)]d\tau + \epsilon \quad (14)$$

Making this the second test of the framework, the quadratic equation is able to simulate different results in reference to the J-flux. The J-flux, diffusion constant, and barrier thickness model the behavior of the chemical under permeability circumstances within a temporal frame.

2.4 Normalized Permeability Diffusion Index Rank Formula (nPDI)

After obtaining values of permeated moles over the barrier of a particular medicine, we must comparatively determine which medicine, not only allowed for the most amount of moles throughout the barrier within a set temporal limit, but also take into account the physio-chemical profile of each individual DoI. While numerous variables could be known to affect a chemical’s permeability, the proponents which predominantly determine permeability are J-flux, diffusion constant, polarity, amount of molecules diffused, molecular weight, and viscosity.

The final part of the framework relies on a composite rank-based score formula which is able to quantify the suitability for a medicine to permeate a barrier. This index, created from the rank-score formula, will be denoted as the normalized Permeability Diffusion Index (nPDI). This index determines which physico-chemical traits had the highest weightage and were most influential in determining the permeability of a certain DoI.

While some factors act as proponents of permeability, with a higher value of the factor leading to a higher permeability, others exhibit an inverse relationship. Correspondingly, factors that have an inverse relationship are represented as $(1 - x)$, so as to penalize an increase in that variable relating to nPDI. In relation to the context of the nPDI formula, larger values of J-flux and diffusion constant typically reveal a chemical’s tendency to permeate more efficiently and at a faster temporal window. Following the same logic, a larger abundance of molecules preceding the barrier, a larger overall molecular weight, and a larger viscosity all relate to a smaller nPDI score. The magnitude of values between different variables necessitates the use of minimum-maximum normalization, which standardizes all values in reference to the largest and smallest values within a dataset. By normalizing all components, we are able to stay within the domain range of [0,1]. Following this, we produce:

$$Y^N = \frac{Y - Y_{min}}{Y_{max} - Y_{min}} \quad (15)$$

$$H(x) = (J_{mag})^N + (D_c)^N + (1 - A)^N + (1 - MW)^N + |P|^N + (1 - \eta_{BTB})^N \quad (16)$$

The above formula represents the min-max normalization. The H(x) function defines the nPDI scale. A variable raised to the N operator is the value which is being min-max normalized in comparison to other values. A condensed version of the formula is given below:

$$H(x) = (J_{mag})^N + (D_c)^N + |P|^N + (3 - A^N + MW^N + \eta_{BTB}^N) \quad (17)$$

Categorization of high and low values within a domain range of [0,1] creates suitability of heat map color-coordination for examining individual variables in each DoI. This process selectively isolates drugs that score comparatively better and diagnoses in which category the medicine seems to exhibit the most permeabilized properties.

2.5 Biophysics-Informed Permeability Framework

Utilization of these three components produces the following mathematical framework by which pharmaceutical drugs can be in-silico methodized:

$$\Phi(J(x), f_a(t), H(x)) = \begin{cases} J(x) = \frac{-(\Delta C x K_B T)}{6\pi\eta r} \\ f_a(t) = \int_0^t [(-J_{mag}\tau)^2 + (\frac{D}{\Delta x}\tau)] d\tau + \epsilon \\ H(x) = (J_{mag})^N + (D_c)^N + |P|^N + (3 - A^N + MW^N + \eta_{BTB}^N) \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

The overall framework, defined by three segmental pieces of $\Phi(x)$, is a model which integrates a biophysics-informed layer to simulate the dynamic changes to the barrier and pharmaceutical interaction. Additionally, the model maps a scale-based component to track highly expressed chemical characteristics. The model integrates parameters into the mobility of the DoI, isolating the in-silico reaction between a BBB and the DoI itself. Using specialized parameters to restrict and numerically evaluate the drug, the permeabilized efficiency of the DoI is quantifiable to a theoretical degree.

The subsequent section details the collection of 25 commonly used oncological or neurological pharmaceuticals. Using open-source data, we subjected these DoIs to the defined in-silico informed pipeline to receive a detailed assessment of scores in chemical characteristics. Rank-based heatmaps will provide insight into which molecules received the highest throughput scores and which parameters had the highest weightage.

3 Biophysic-Informed Pipeline Throughput Assessment of 25 Oncological Drugs

3.1 Experimental Precursors

This section will cover the experimental process of subjecting 25 oncological drugs into this pipeline for validation of this model. As an acknowledgement, all of the coding principles that are depicted in this paper are pseudocode, and do not display the language of a specific coding IDE. The algorithmic framework presented is written using Python, specifically BioPython, and uses computational libraries for data processing. Specifically, the following libraries were used: Pandas, Entrez (BioPython), Statistics, Matplotlib, Seaborn, Requests, Pubchempy.

The pharmaceutical drugs used for this study were all FDA-approved and have been either introduced recently as a promising medication or have a reputable nature as being an oncological medication. Due to the computational-directionality of this project, other credible chemical-software have been used for data extraction and will be cited.

3.2 Hybridized Fickian Equation Application

3.2.1 PubChem Data Collection

The first objective of this experiment is to collect necessary data which could be used to perform the first layer of the model: the Fickian-hybridized equation. To perform this test, the variables which are necessary include the standard BBB’s viscosity, spherical radii of chemicals, standard homeostatic internal temperature, standard barrier thickness, initial chemical concentration and Stefan-Boltzmann’s constant. This section will detail what coding procedures were used to retrieve these variables.

All 25 drugs listed have been assigned a unique identifier as part of the PubChem database of FDA-approved medication, SMILES. The coding procedure follows a search algorithm, using PubChemPy and Pandas, which can retrieve the chemical’s name, molecular formula, molecular weight (molar mass), WPC/OPC, Polarity (XlogP), Hydrogen Acceptor count and Hydrogen Donor count. Using a search algorithm to pull these characteristics, they are appended into a list shown below:

Table 2: Physicochemical Properties of the 25 FDA-Approved Medications

#	Name	Formula	MW (Da)	WPC/OPC	Polarity	HBA	HBD
0	Levodopa	C ₉ H ₁₁ NO ₄	197.19	-2.7	Polar	5	4
1	Carbidopa	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄	226.23	-2.2	Polar	6	5
2	Levetiracetam	C ₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	170.21	-0.3	Slightly Polar	2	1
3	Gabapentin	C ₉ H ₁₇ NO ₂	171.24	-1.1	Polar	3	2
4	Phenobarbital	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃	232.23	1.5	Nonpolar	3	2
5	Phenytoin	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	252.27	2.5	Nonpolar	2	2
6	Diazepam	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O	284.74	3.0	Nonpolar	2	0
7	Buspirone	C ₂₁ H ₃₁ N ₅ O ₂	385.50	2.6	Nonpolar	6	0
8	Ceftriaxone	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₈ O ₇ S ₃	554.60	-1.3	Polar	13	4
9	Vancomycin	C ₆₆ H ₇₅ Cl ₂ N ₉ O ₂₄	1449.20	-2.6	Polar	26	19
10	Fluconazole	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ F ₂ N ₆ O	306.27	0.4	Slightly Nonpolar	7	1
11	Temozolomide	C ₆ H ₆ N ₆ O ₂	194.15	-1.1	Polar	5	1
12	Lomustine	C ₉ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂	233.69	2.8	Nonpolar	3	1
13	Methotrexate	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₅	454.40	-1.8	Polar	12	5
14	Carmustine	C ₅ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂	214.05	1.5	Nonpolar	3	1
15	Etoposide	C ₂₉ H ₃₂ O ₁₃	588.60	0.6	Slightly Nonpolar	13	3
16	Vorasidenib	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ ClF ₆ N ₆	414.74	5.3	Nonpolar	12	2
17	Tovorafenib	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ F ₃ N ₇ O ₂ S	506.30	3.0	Nonpolar	11	3
18	Dexamethasone	C ₂₂ H ₂₉ FO ₅	392.50	1.9	Nonpolar	6	3
19	Metronidazole	C ₆ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	171.15	0.0	Slightly Nonpolar	4	1
20	Doxorubicin	C ₂₇ H ₂₉ NO ₁₁	543.50	1.3	Nonpolar	12	6
21	Paclitaxel	C ₄₇ H ₅₁ NO ₁₄	853.90	2.5	Nonpolar	14	4
22	Erlotinib	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₄	393.40	3.3	Nonpolar	7	1
23	Loperamide	C ₂₉ H ₃₃ ClN ₂ O ₂	477.00	5.0	Nonpolar	3	1
24	Gefitinib	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ ClFN ₄ O ₃	446.90	4.1	Nonpolar	8	1

To determine what constitutes within the categories of nonpolar, slightly nonpolar, slightly polar, and polar, we use a comparison function to categorize the chemicals based on their XlogP value, which is also appended from the PubChem database. The function shows:

Algorithm 1 Polarity Categorization based on XlogP

```

1: procedure CLASSIFYPOLARITY( $XlogP$ )
2:   if  $XlogP < -1$  then
3:     return "Polar"
4:   else if  $XlogP > 1$  then
5:     return "Nonpolar"
6:   else if  $-1 \leq XlogP \leq 0$  then
7:     return "Slightly Polar"
8:   else if  $0 \leq XlogP \leq 1$  then
9:     return "Slightly Nonpolar"
10:  end if
11: end procedure

```

3.2.2 Hybridized Fickian Equation Coding Procedures and Results

The collected values can now be used in the derived Fickian equation as presented in section 2. This equation is presented below:

$$J(\eta, T, r, \Delta Cx) = \frac{-(\Delta Cx K_B T)}{6\pi\eta r} \quad (19)$$

Using BioPython, we are able to use values appended into the characterized list (List I), to produce respective values for spherical radii, diffusion constants, J-fluxes, molecular weight, J-magnitude, and additional attributes. The additional attributes confers the value of β as assigned in subsection 2.2. A β value of 1 corresponds to a standard state, as this is where the viscosity is ideally the η_{BBB} . Constants used for determined values of η_{BBB} , K_B , T , ΔCx are provided in Table 1.

Noticngly, to derive the value of MR, the rederivation for spherical radii requires the value of molar refractivity, which is sparse in PubChem databases.

$$sr = \sqrt[3]{\frac{3MR}{(6.022 \times 10^{23})(4\pi)}} \quad (20)$$

Utilizing the Swiss ADME [10] molecular drug design website, a functionality of this website is its SMILE analysis and information retrieval. Importantly, this tool provides an accurate estimation of the drug’s refractive index, which is synonymous with the molar refractivity for the purposes of this experiment. A python script generates the throughput assessment of each of the 25 drug’s respective SMILES codes along with their accompanying molar refractivity index. Using this calculated value, we are able to use equation 2. Appending these values into a list, we produce the following:

Table 3: Calculated Chemical Transport Properties

#	Name	Radii	$D_{constant}$	MW
0	Levodopa	2.698	2.104	197.19
1	Carbidopa	2.830	2.006	226.23
2	Levetiracetam	2.677	2.121	170.21
3	Gabapentin	2.660	2.134	171.24
4	Phenobarbital	2.993	1.897	232.23
5	Phenytoin	3.132	1.812	252.27
6	Diazepam	3.267	1.738	284.74
7	Buspirone	3.610	1.572	385.50
8	Ceftriaxone	3.761	1.509	554.60
9	Vancomycin	5.160	1.100	1449.2
10	Fluconazole	3.038	1.869	306.27
11	Temozolomide	2.601	2.182	194.15
12	Lomustine	2.861	1.984	233.69
13	Methotrexate	3.607	1.574	454.40
14	Carmustine	2.647	2.145	214.05
15	Etoposide	3.806	1.491	588.60
16	Vorasidenib	3.246	1.749	414.74
17	Tovorafenib	3.535	1.606	506.30
18	Dexamethasone	3.432	1.654	392.50
19	Metronidazole	2.579	2.201	171.15
20	Doxorubicin	3.747	1.515	543.50
21	Paclitaxel	4.428	1.282	853.90
22	Erlotinib	3.535	1.606	393.40
23	Loperamide	3.834	1.481	477.00
24	Gefitinib	3.640	1.559	446.90

Spherical Radii and Diffusion Constants are scaled by 10^{-10} . For all compounds, $\beta_{constant} = 1$.

3.3 Temporal-Concentration Quadratic Application to Dataset

3.3.1 Constructing the In-Silico Temporal-Concentration Quadratic

After performing the first test, our code outputs Tables 2 and 3, which combined gives us calculated values of J-flux, J-magnitude, molecular weight, calculated diffusion constant, spherical radii, and a standard attribute. These pieces of information will be crucial to the second layer of the framework, which describes an integrable temporal concentration quadratic, equation 12, as noted below:

$$f_a(t) = \int_0^t [(-J_{mag}\tau)^2 + (\frac{D}{\Delta x}\tau)]d\tau + \epsilon \quad (21)$$

Values for constants, such as Δx , is noted in Table A. The following equation is coded using the Python math library. To make this integral mathematically visible within standard window settings, the J-magnitude was multiplied by a factor of $(-1 \cdot 10^{-4})$. Similarly, the beta-value is the $\frac{D}{\Delta x}$, which is the Diffusion constant divided by a barrier thickness of 200 nm:

Table 4: Model Coefficients of Transformed Temporal Quadratic $f(t) = \alpha t^2 + \rho t + \epsilon$

#	Name	J-Mag	α	ρ	#	Name	J-Mag	α	ρ
0	Levodopa	0.0010	-10.52	1.05	13	Methotrexate	0.0008	-7.87	0.79
1	Carbidopa	0.0010	-10.03	1.00	14	Carmustine	0.0011	-10.72	1.07
2	Levetiracetam	0.0011	-10.60	1.06	15	Etoposide	0.0007	-7.46	0.75
3	Gabapentin	0.0011	-10.67	1.07	16	Vorasidenib	0.0009	-8.74	0.87
4	Phenobarbital	0.0009	-9.48	0.95	17	Tovorafenib	0.0008	-8.03	0.80
5	Phenytoin	0.0009	-9.06	0.91	18	Dexamethasone	0.0008	-8.27	0.83
6	Diazepam	0.0009	-8.69	0.87	19	Metronidazole	0.0011	-11.01	1.10
7	Buspirone	0.0008	-7.86	0.79	20	Doxorubicin	0.0008	-7.58	0.76
8	Ceftriaxone	0.0008	-7.55	0.75	21	Paclitaxel	0.0006	-6.41	0.64
9	Vancomycin	0.0006	-5.50	0.55	22	Erlotinib	0.0008	-8.03	0.80
10	Fluconazole	0.0009	-9.34	0.93	23	Loperamide	0.0007	-7.40	0.74
11	Temozolomide	0.0011	-10.91	1.09	24	Gefitinib	0.0008	-7.80	0.78
12	Lomustine	0.0010	-9.92	0.99					

ρ values are scaled by 10^{-12} . All ϵ Brownian constants = 20.

3.3.2 Molecular Diffusivity Through The BBB and Area Graphs

Producing the following quadratics, heuristics, now enables the usage of mathematically depicting the integral which is bound by $t = 0$ and $t = \lambda$. For the units of the temporal window, seconds most aptly describes the common time of early-scale diffusion through the BBB when the medication is first introduced into the body. Due to these reasons, the lambda-time constraint was set at $\lambda = 0.5$ seconds. Involving the integral section of the temporal quadratic requires the use of Sympy and Numpy for calculating the actual area, or integral, from the domain range of $t \in [0, \lambda]$. Time constraints on the diffusion of these molecules allows us to deduct the amount of molecules which are preceding the barrier, or haven't passed the BBB within the 0.5 second window. This value will also be important in determining the nDPI-associated weighted value for each function, relating to their diffusive power over a barrier. The table output shows:

Table 5: Calculated Molecular Diffused Area for Compounds

#	Name	Area	#	Name	Area
0	Levodopa	9.5617	13	Methotrexate	9.6722
1	Carbidopa	9.5822	14	Carmustine	9.5532
2	Levetiracetam	9.5582	15	Etoposide	9.6893
3	Gabapentin	9.5554	16	Vorasidenib	9.6357
4	Phenobarbital	9.6049	17	Tovorafenib	9.6655
5	Phenytoin	9.6224	18	Dexamethasone	9.6554
6	Diazepam	9.6380	19	Metronidazole	9.5414
7	Buspirone	9.6724	20	Doxorubicin	9.6844
8	Ceftriaxone	9.6855	21	Paclitaxel	9.7329
9	Vancomycin	9.7708	22	Erlotinib	9.6654
10	Fluconazole	9.6107	23	Loperamide	9.6916
11	Temozolomide	9.5454	24	Gefitinib	9.6751
12	Lomustine	9.5867			

Accompanying the amount of molecules which have not passed the barrier at $t = 0.5$ seconds, Matplotlib utilities can functionally graph corresponding quadratic curves based on the equation, along with the area enclosed within the two constraints of $t = 0$ and $t = 0.5$. This algorithm was able to generate an accompanying graph to each drug, along with their area-value. The dashed line is symbolic of the λ constraint. An example of the temporal quadratic graph is given below for Levodopa:

Figure 1: Area Graph of Levodopa Molecule after $\lambda = 0.5$

3.4 nPDI Scalar $H(x)$ Formula Application

The last layer of the framework consists of the nPDI-scalar formula along with minimum-maximum normalization for standardizing large scale values within the whole dataset. We apply min-max normalization to all variables contained within the dataset for each individual FDA drug. The normalized table of all nPDI-scale variables are obtained:

Table 6: Min-Max Normalized Transport Parameters

#	Name	J-Mag	Area	MW	#	Name	J-Mag	Area	MW
0	Levodopa	.9114	.0886	.0211	13	Methotrexate	.4300	.5700	.2222
1	Carbidopa	.8223	.1777	.0438	14	Carmustine	.9485	.0515	.0343
2	Levetiracetam	.9268	.0732	.0000	15	Etoposide	.3553	.6447	.3271
3	Gabapentin	.9388	.0612	.0008	16	Vorasidenib	.5889	.4111	.1912
4	Phenobarbital	.7233	.2767	.0485	17	Tovorafenib	.4592	.5408	.2628
5	Phenytoin	.6468	.3532	.0642	18	Dexamethasone	.5030	.4970	.1738
6	Diazepam	.5789	.4211	.0895	19	Metronidazole	1.000	.0000	.0007
7	Buspirone	.4288	.5712	.1683	20	Doxorubicin	.3769	.6231	.2919
8	Ceftriaxone	.3717	.6283	.3005	21	Paclitaxel	.1653	.8347	.5346
9	Vancomycin	.0000	1.000	1.000	22	Erlotinib	.4593	.5407	.1745
10	Fluconazole	.6979	.3021	.1064	23	Loperamide	.3455	.6545	.2399
11	Temozolomide	.9826	.0174	.0187	24	Gefitinib	.4171	.5829	.2163
12	Lomustine	.8026	.1974	.0496					

Using the values from each row, designated to the specific drug, we perform a calculation with equation 12, the nPDI equation, to produce the Heatmap number list. This list will determine the visualization of the heatmap generation and

how, comparatively, the drugs express permeability-favored traits with reference to one another. The heatmap diagrams will be expressed in the results section:

Table 7: Overall nDPI Score Distributions through H(x) function

#	Chemical Name	Value	#	Chemical Name	Value
0	Levodopa	5.2186	13	Methotrexate	3.4035
1	Carbidopa	4.8341	14	Carmustine	5.0904
2	Levetiracetam	4.8331	15	Etoposide	2.8479
3	Gabapentin	5.0191	16	Vorasidenib	4.5716
4	Phenobarbital	4.4003	17	Tovorafenib	3.6769
5	Phenytoin	4.3440	18	Dexamethasone	3.6898
6	Diazepam	4.2091	19	Metronidazole	4.9953
7	Buspirone	3.6047	20	Doxorubicin	3.0800
8	Ceftriaxone	3.0557	21	Paclitaxel	2.4289
9	Vancomycin	1.4866	22	Erlotinib	3.8222
10	Fluconazole	4.0588	23	Loperamide	3.7359
11	Temozolomide	5.1326	24	Gefitinib	3.8047
12	Lomustine	4.8826			

4 Results of Throughput Assessment Framework

The final experimental section of this paper includes the results of this comparative study. Incorporating the results we received from the min-max normalized transport parameters (Table 6) and the overall nDPI score distributions for each chemical (Table 7), we are able to make two different corresponding heat maps. The Table 6 heatmap, below, uses the normalized values of each individual drug and ranks their score through a color-contrast heat map scale. The second heatmap, Table 7, uses the nDPI score calculated from the H(x) formula to output the scores of each drug in a similar fashion, through a color contrast scale. Within both of the heatmaps, a more saturated color signifies a larger score and inversely true. The purpose of these numerical heatmaps are to qualitatively depict which factors that are most deterministic in permeability along with which FDA pharmaceuticals scored the highest through the three-layered permeability framework.

Figure 2: Visual representation of the heat map distribution.

From Diagram I, we see the following graphical depiction of the results of our experimentation. Initial observations of this heatmap show the first 4 indexed chemicals, Levodopa through Gabapentin, along with Temozolomide, Carmustine, and Metronidazole to have a high distribution of physicochemical permeabilized qualities and had high normalization scores for J-magnitude and the Diffusion constant, both factors which correlate directly to permeability. Inversely, (1-x) reciprocal factors such as area and molecular weight were expressed highest in Vancomycin, with both factors being normalized to 1.00, indicating Vancomycin itself attained the highest numerical area and molecular weight. This can be further reaffirmed by the chemical formula of Vancomycin, $C_{66}H_{75}Cl_2N_9O_{24}$, and its medical usage. Not only does the chemical formula indicate the large molecular weight, it also describes why Vancomycin is rarely used for CNS-based operations due to its large size which would be more suitable for bloodstream based routes. The final category of polarity indicates a low weightage on the true permeability of a certain chemical itself. While Vorasidenib and Loperamide showed high saturation in polarity, it does not equate to a specific trait within either chemicals themselves.

Figure 3: Overall nDPI-Scale Scores

Based on the overall physicochemical score distributions, the nDPI scale, Diagram II displays the quantitative combination of all factors presented within Diagram I, with both favorable permeabilized factors and reciprocal (1-x) factors, to create an over $H(x)$ nDPI score for the FDA chemical. Following the generation of this heatmap, Levodopa scored the highest nDPI-scaled score of 5.22. Conversely, Vancomycin scored an nDPI-scaled score of 1.49. Both results are corresponding to their individual score saturations for each variable within Diagram 1, with Levodopa having a score of 0.91 for both J-Magnitude and Diffusion constant. Similarly, Levodopa scored remarkably low in molecular barrier area and molecular weight, scoring 0.02 and 0.09 respectively. This distinction of permeability-favoring qualities is why Levodopa is a very common form of treatment. Levodopa has been a confirmed pharmaceutical which is able to pass the BBB, and can even further break down into its dopamine components to disperse within the CNS after diffusing through the barrier [11]. Similarly, there is a correlation between the utility of the medicine and their respective ranking within the nDPI-scale, validating the capabilities of the framework.

In conclusion, with the use of heatmaps, nDPI-scores can be qualitatively and quantitatively expressed through their weightages and how permeable they were in comparison to other medicine within the experimental group. This framework, a combination of a fickian-derived biophysical equation, a temporal permeability test through a barrier $t=$, and an established and normalized scale for overall physicochemical pharmaceutical kinetic favorability, is representative of how drugs are manufactured for certain purposes and exhibit certain distinct qualities. This mathematical framework was able to selectively weight permeable characteristics while penalizing non-permeabilizing characteristics.

5 Conclusion, Limitations, and Future Adaptions

In-silico representation of medicinal models proves to be a growing field of study, as more validated datasets, improvements in experimental predictions, artificial intelligence training information, and mathematical-informed models become a standardized way of integrating medicine into mathematics. As important as the wet-lab focused experiments are for clinical trials, the usage of virtual scientific principles to guide educated predictions and future hypotheses equally influence the future of medicine.

The aim of this study was to provide an integrated model which can bridge the gap between common biological phenomena, permeability, and manipulating mathematical formulas to descriptively model this in a theoretical state space. While clinical trials remain the most validated method of pharmaceutical experimentation, the hybridized, parametrized, framework provides theoretical boundaries to the movement of molecules. This framework is able to provide educated hypotheses into behavior of pharmaceuticals without the use of selective in-vivo testing.

Despite this, a large drawback of this model is due to the lack of physical experimentation to validate the numerical output of this model and its comparative power. Due to this, this framework should be considered a pre-clinical pharmaceutical tool and not for human clinical advisory. A future extension to this study is the use of, if available, wet-lab experimentation for measuring the permeability of these drugs over a mimical BBB. In addition, future adaptations into this framework include the use of Markov Models to produce idealized weights for a compromised BBB, BTB. This would provide larger insight into pharmaceutical behavior under a variable state, one which deviates from the standardized BBB environment explored in this paper.

As we approach a society which is becoming more advanced in the field of medicine and improving the quality of life for others, it is crucial to address the importance of a combination of both wet and in-silico based work. This combination is powerful, accelerating the field to become more personalized to the health of every person. Since each individual is complex, providing this medicinal-mathematical framework could push to integrate the gaping hole that is one-dimensional science. Open science is the future, a transformative time of witnessing the combination of mankind through the combination of medicine and mathematics.

6 Citations and Reference Sources

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